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**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
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1. Abstract

Crop rotation and nutrition are essential elements of soil cultivation, and it is a powerful agricultural practice for improving soil health and to reduce inter-annual yield variability. A long-term experiment (1984 – 2022) in Borovce (near to Piešťany, western Slovakia, 167 m a.s.l., 48°34'45.5"N, 17°43'47.5"E) was conducted to evaluate determine the effect of 40 % 60 % and 80 % proportion of cereals in crop rotation and two nutrient treatments (H1 – combination of mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizer Veget® and H2 mineral fertilization) on stability and grain yield of winter wheat. Crop rotation had a significant impact on the grain yield of winter wheat ($P < 0.05$) whereas the addition of organic fertilizer Veget® to mineral fertilizer did not show any significant effect on grain yield. The least stable winter wheat grain yield was provided by H1 nutrient treatment (combined minthel and organic fertilizers) and H2 nutrient treatment (mineral fertilizers) with the 80 % proportion of cereals (rank 5 and rank 6), respectively.

2. Introduction

Crop rotations is the traditional base for agriculture in all Europe dating back to the Romans who practiced a two-course rotation. Arable land was divided into two fields i.e. one field was planted by cereal while the other as fallow till the next season to recover the fertility (Savio 2011). The Romans and later, in many countries of Europe, the three-course rotation was practiced with autumn corn, spring corn and fallow. This system lasted more than 15 centuries. Nowadays, crop rotation represents the essential element of soil cultivation (Woźniak, 2019) and it is considered as a good method to maintain healthy soil, to improve crop resilience and to prevent problems with weed and pest infestation (Jalli et al., 2021, Smith et al., 2023).

At the beginning of the last century economic pressures and a high demand of agricultural crops brought to a higher number of rotations even till six-course rotation (e.g. roots-barley-seeds-potatoes-wheat-oats), introducing high-value crops such as sugar beet, potatoes, cereals. Similarly in Slovakia, crop rotations have been constantly adapted to economic conditions over the past 50 years (Babulicová and Gavurníková, 2015). To improve the profitability of agricultural farms, the so-called "free crop rotation" with a maximum of 2 or 3 crops have been widely used. However, winter wheat grain yield was significantly lower with cereal monoculture (Babulicová, 2015; Carr et al., 2006). The importation of fertilizers into the farm system and the improved machinery allowed many advantages on one had but brought increasing economic pressures in terms of capital costs and labour on the other hand. Technological development allowed to farmers to move from the concept of strict rotation to monocultures without or only with occasional brakes. This situation allowed to have higher profitability but not without environmental consequences which may be no longer acceptable and bring a threat to the future of agriculture (Liang et al. 2023).

In many cases of monocultural systems it is observed a decline in yields. This event is called by someone 'soil sickness'. This 'soil sickness' is often poorly cured with the use of more fertilizers from an external source. Without the addition of fertilizers many crops remove large amounts of nutrients from the soil. Even the effects of residues on the next crop may be important. Many of these are antibiotic in behaviour and may block the activity of soil organisms. Microbial action on crop residues may also produce toxic substances which inhibit

the germination of new crops. Pests and diseases that transfer from one crop to the other can be reduced. E.g. Potato or cereal nematodes, wireworms, etc. are examples of problems which can be controlled by good rotational design (Toor et al. 2021). Well rotational design is the most essential component of farming systems. The rotation must maintain soil fertility, levels of organic matter, soil structure. Rotation has at the same time to ensure that nutrients are not wasted (Benini et al. 2023). The principal mean of rotations is to control weeds, pests and diseases in the agricultural system. In few words the rotation must be carefully designed to meet all these objectives. It must be considered the soil type and texture, climatic conditions, type of crops, livestock on the farm. Within the cropping limitations imposed by the environmental conditions many guidelines should be observed. Inter alia: a) Deep rooting crops should follow shallow rooting crops; b) N fixing crops should alternate with N demanding crops; c) alternate between leaf and straw crops; d) alternate between autumn sown and spring sown crops (Tanverer et al., 2019). In conclusion, rotation can help to manage soil fertility, improve health of soils, increase the availability of nutrients for crops and reduce erosion.

Winter wheat is the most widespread crop in the world. In Slovakia, it is grown in all regions and its area covers more than 50% of the total area used to grow cereals. Although winter wheat is a crop of a continental climate, and it is also suitable for warmer and drier conditions. However, the current period of climate change with the occurrence of a lack of precipitation and periods of heat with extremely high temperatures poses a serious risk for achieving sufficient yields of this crop.

The aim of our research was to provide insights into the impact of crop rotation with various proportion of cereals and weather on grain yield and yield stability of winter wheat, utilizing data form the Borovce long-term experiment.

3. Material and methods

The Borovce (167 m a.s.l., 48°34'45.5"N 17°43'47.5"E) long-term experiment was set up at in 1974 in Slovakia near Piešťany.

Figure 1 The Borovce long-term experiment

The soil type was Luvic Chernozem (IUSS, 2022). The parent material was loess, the arable layer had a loamy texture with a humus horizon thickness of app. 40 – 50 cm. At start of experiment the soil pH was 5.5 – 7.2, the humus content was 1.8 – 2.0 %, content of plant available phosphorus and plant available potassium was medium, as well. The Continental climate with mild winter and warm summer has long-term mean annual temperature (1981-2010) of 9.7°C and a mean long-term annual sum of precipitation of 567 m.

Experimental design

The LTE was arranged in randomized complete blocks with four replications and the individual size plot was 6 m x 8 m. In the LTE, three types of crop rotation with different proportion of cereals (40 %, 60 % and 60 %) were compared. The proportion of cereals is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Crop rotations in Borovce

Year	Proportion of cereals in crop rotations (%)		
	40 % cereals	60 % cereals	80 % cereals
1	Pea	Pea	Winter wheat
2	Winter wheat	Winter wheat	Spring barley
3	Silage maize	Winter barley	Pea
4	Spring barley	Silage maize	Winter wheat
5	Grain maize	Spring barley	Winter barley

Two nutrient treatments used in this LTE were: H1 – combination of mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizer Veget® and H2 mineral fertilization. Nitrogen fertilizers were split to pre-sowing fertilization in autumn, application in early spring and the last one at the growth stage BBCH 37. Phosphorus and potassium were applied in autumn before sowing, and their doses were calculated according to balance method. Organic manure Veget® in a dose of 5 t. ha⁻¹ was applied in autumn. The composition of organic fertilizer Veget® was as follows: dry matter content minimum was 85% (includes combustible matter content 75%); pH_{H2O} 8.5, C:N ratio was 13:1, content of total N, P₂O₅ and K₂O was 2.5 – 3.0%; 0.5 – 2.0 %; 1.5%, respectively. The field management such as soil tillage (plough to a depth of 25 cm), crop protection and weed control followed the general agronomic practice. Winter wheat with the seeding rate of 450 seeds. m⁻² was sown no later than 10 October.

3. Results and discussion

1.1. Temperature and Precipitation during Long-Term Experiment

Since 1985, the mean annual temperature has significantly increased by 0.01°C (P < 0.05) at the Borovce site. The highest mean annual temperatures were recorded in 2002, 2003, 2007, 2008, 2009, while in 2008 the deviation from the long-term normal (1981-2010) was up to +2.02 °C (Figure 2). Below-normal temperatures were also recorded during the period. The mean annual temperature was lower by 2.75 °C, 2.45 °C and 2.08 °C in 1985, 1986 and 1987 respectively.

The annual total precipitation showed decreasing trend but statistically insignificant (Figure 3). The highest annual total precipitation was recorded in 2010 (895 mm). Conversely, the

lowest sum of precipitation was found in 2003 (384 mm), 2022 (417 mm) (Figure 3). The years 2017 and 2018 were also characterized by a low precipitation, when the annual total precipitation was 20% and 16% lower compared to the long-term annual total precipitation.

Figure 2 Relationship between the mean annual temperature and long-term normal (1981-2010)

Figure 3 Relationship between the annual total precipitation and long-term normal (1981-2010)

1.2. Relationship between grain yield and weather conditions

The relationship (Figure 4 and 5) between winter wheat grain yield and mean annual temperature was negative, nevertheless not statistically significant ($r = -0.004$, $P = 0.614$). The positive relationship between grain yield and annual total precipitation was found ($r = 0.186$, $P = 0.000$).

Figure 4 Relationship between grain yield and daily mean annual temperature

Figure 5 Relationship between grain yield and total annual precipitation

1.3. Relationship between grain yield and cereals proportion in crop rotation

The lowest grain yield (3.99 t.ha⁻¹) was recorded in 1986 in crop rotation with the 80 % proportion of cereals at the H1 nutrient treatment. Winter wheat grain yield exceeded 8.00 t.ha⁻¹ in 1994, 1996 and 2001 with all types of nutrient treatments and cereals proportion as well (Figure 6 and 7). In 1994 and 1996, the mean daily temperature and total annual precipitation were similar to long-term normal. Apart of total annual precipitation, monthly distribution of precipitation impacts the grain yield of cereals. Some studies (Gandia et al., 2021, Hlisnikovský et al., 2022) confirmed that sufficient precipitation in April and May has a positive effect on grain yield.

Figure 6 Development of grain yield of H1 nutrient treatment with combination of mineral fertilizer with organic fertilizer Veget®

Figure 7 Development of grain yield of H2 nutrient treatment with mineral fertilizers

Crop rotation had a significant impact on the grain yield of winter wheat ($P < 0.05$). Results are shown in Table 2. Within the experimental period, significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower grain yield was noted for crop rotation with the 80 % proportion of cereals, whereas crop rotations with the 40 % and 60 % proportion of cereals showed the average grain yield of 6.85 t.ha⁻¹. Positive effect of crop rotation diversity on grain yield reported Smith et al. (2023). In contrary to crop rotation, the addition of organic fertilizer Veget® to mineral fertilizer did not show any significant effect on grain yield. Similarly to Borovce LTE, Kunzová and Hejčman (2009) showed that winter wheat grain yield was not significantly affected by mineral fertilization in the first decade of 50-years Ivanovice Crop Rotation Experiment established on a degraded chernozem in 1955 in the Czech Republic.

Table 2. Grain yield of winter wheat ($\text{t}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$) for different proportion of cereals in crop rotation and nutrient treatment over experimental period

		Mean	Min	Max
Proportion of cereals in crop rotation	40 %	$6.85 \pm 1.09^{\text{B}}$	3.81	8.59
	60 %	$6.84 \pm 1.17^{\text{B}}$	3.91	8.65
	80 %	$6.54 \pm 1.29^{\text{A}}$	2.83	8.93
Nutrient treatment	H1	$6.80 \pm 1.21^{\text{A}}$	2.83	8.78
	H2	$6.69 \pm 1.18^{\text{A}}$	3.25	8.66

1.4. Grain yield stability

Kang's rank-sum statistic showed that the least stable winter wheat grain yield was provided by H1 nutrient treatment (combined mineral and organic fertilizers) and H2 nutrient treatment (mineral fertilizers) with the 80 % proportion of cereals (rank 5 and rank 6), respectively (Table 3). To contrary, the highest stability showed the H1 nutrient treatment (combined mineral and organic fertilizers) with 40 % proportion of cereals (rank 1). The results show that diversified crop rotation positively impact grain yield (Garbelini et al., 2022). Similarly, the application of mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizer Veget[®] showed higher yield stability than solely mineral fertilizers.

Table 3. Grain yield stability

Nutrient treatment	Proportion of cereals in crop rotation	Mean Yield	Rank Mean Yield	Rank Stability	Kang Stability Index
H1	40%	6,88	2	2	4
H2	40%	6,82	3	1	4
H1	60%	6,89	1	4	5
H2	60%	6,79	4	3	7
H1	80%	6,63	5	6	11
H2	80%	6,44	6	5	11

4. Conclusions

In the Borovce long-term experiment grain yield of winter wheat was mainly affected by crop rotation. Significantly lower grain yield was recorded with the 80 % proportion of cereals. Type of nutrition presented by combination of mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizer Veget[®] or solely mineral fertilization did not show significant impact on grain yield probably due to basic fertility of chernozem in Borovce.

Over the experimental period, the mean annual temperature has significantly increased by 0.01°C. To contrary, annual total precipitation showed decreasing trend but statistically insignificant. Regarding impact of weather on grain yield, the positive relationship between grain yield and annual total precipitation was found.

Concerning grain yield stability, more stable grain yield are provided by crop rotation with 40 % proportion of cereals and application of combination of mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizer Veget[®]. Conversely, the least stable grain yield was found for by crop rotation with 80 % proportion of cereals.

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